

THE PLACE OF GENERAL COMPETENCE IN THE HIGHER MILITARY EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract: The article is devoted to the development of general cultural competence in future military officers, which is one of the important factors in the successful implementation of the military educator's pedagogical activity. The article substantiates the content of the concepts of general cultural competence in the educational process.

Keywords: general cultural competence, culture and enlightenment, education, process, military, system.

Introduction. It is no secret that our country is carrying out significant work in the field of education. The most urgent issues are the radical improvement of the military education system, the identification of targeted areas for the training of specialists with higher education, especially the continuous improvement of the professional qualifications and knowledge level of military pedagogical personnel. The widespread use of the achievements of science and innovation in the world education system, the consistent and sustainable development of all spheres of society and state life are becoming an important factor in building a worthy future for the country. In countries such as Japan, the USA, Finland, Korea, Russia, and China, the training of highly professionally competent, competitive personnel is considered the main direction of development, and innovations in education, including modern, interactive and creative teaching methods, are being widely introduced.

Main part. Future military officers need to have their own personal abilities to develop general cultural competence, and to achieve this success requires great responsibility from them. The management process is considered to be an awareness of special skills, knowledge, and qualifications, and in this process, the officer must demonstrate such qualities as self-confidence, emotional balance, superiority, stress resistance, creativity, striving for success, entrepreneurial spirit, responsibility, reliability in performing tasks, independence, and sociability.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Education in the new edition of 2020 and the new Development Strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 set out directions for a radical reform of education, which include freeing education from outdated ideological views, solving the problems of the continuous education system, and

developing the current education system in accordance with our national mentality. Today, the implementation of the tasks set for military higher educational institutions requires not only changing the content, forms and methods of cadets' activities, but also reviewing the activities of professors and teachers.

The concept of "competence" entered the field of education as a result of psychological research. Therefore, competence means "how a specialist behaves in unconventional situations, in unexpected cases, enters into dialogue, takes a new path in relations with opponents, performs ambiguous tasks, uses information full of contradictions, has a plan of action in consistently developing and complex processes."

Universal competence is a person's ability to act in the cultural space. It includes national and universal culture, family, social phenomena and the spiritual and moral foundations of traditions.

General cultural competencies - this is the ability to successfully act, based on practical experience, knowledge and skills, in solving problems that are characteristic of many types of non-professional and professional activities.

General cultural competencies develop during the mastery of the content of general subject courses and professional modules. General cultural competencies represent a set of socio-personal characteristics, and the possession of this set of characteristics means a person's ability to successfully perform professional and non-professional tasks of a universal nature.

General cultural competencies include generalized methods of activity that allow a person to master cultural patterns and create new ones. In this regard, this competency is divided into such parts as information-cognitive activity, which includes cognitive activity, social coordination activity, which includes the ability to perform social functions, and communicative activity, which includes methods of organizing information exchange and joint activities.

We imagine universal cultural competence as a result of education, reflecting the knowledge of the specific features of universal human culture and national culture, the foundations of spiritual and moral relations and social phenomena, traditions, their practical application in the system of social relations, the presence of ideas about the scientific worldview and the presence of experience in the field of mastering the cultural space.

The professional activity of cadets of a higher military educational institution is considered a difficult and honorable profession. In an era of rapid innovative development, this profession encourages a person to be in constant search, develop, improve professionally, spiritually, educationally, culturally. Such a requirement

plays an important role in increasing the universal cultural competence of future officers.

Professional competence is the acquisition of knowledge, skills and competencies necessary for the implementation of professional activities by a specialist and their high-level application in practice.

Professional competence does not imply the acquisition of separate knowledge and skills by a specialist, but the mastery of integrative knowledge and actions in each independent area. Competence also requires the constant enrichment of professional knowledge, the study of new information, the ability to understand important social requirements, the ability to search for new information, process it and apply it in one's activities.

The essence of the qualities that are reflected in the basis of professional competence is briefly described below.

1. Social competence is the ability to be active in social relations, the ability to possess skills, and the ability to communicate with subjects in professional activities.

2. Special competence - preparation for the organization of professional and pedagogical activities, rational solution of professional and pedagogical tasks, realistic assessment of the results of activities, consistent development of the BKM, and psychological, methodological, informational, creative, innovative and communicative competence are highlighted at the heart of this competence. They express the following content:

1) psychological competence - the ability to create a healthy psychological environment in the pedagogical process, organize positive dialogue with cadets and other participants in the educational process, timely understanding and elimination of various negative psychological conflicts;

2) methodological competence - the ability to methodologically rational organization of the pedagogical process, correctly determine the forms of educational or educational activities, select methods and means in accordance with the purpose, effectively apply methods, successfully apply tools;

3) information competence - searching for, collecting, sorting, processing necessary, important, useful information in the information environment and using it purposefully, appropriately, effectively;

4) creative competence - a critical, creative approach to pedagogical activity, the ability to demonstrate one's own creative skills;

5) innovative competence - putting forward new ideas to improve the pedagogical process, improve the quality of education, increase the effectiveness of the educational process, and effectively implementing them in practice;

6) communicative competence - being in sincere communication with all

participants in the educational process, including cadets, being able to listen to them, and having a positive impact on them.

3. Personal competence - consistently achieving professional growth, increasing the level of qualifications, and demonstrating one's internal capabilities in professional activities.

4. Technological competence - mastering advanced technologies that enrich the professional and pedagogical BKM, using modern tools, techniques and technologies.

5. Extreme competence - having the ability to make rational decisions and act correctly in emergency situations (natural disasters, technological process failures), when pedagogical conflicts arise.

A military educator, first of all, must have reached a high professional level, that is, be a master of his profession both as a military specialist and as a teacher. Therefore, he must embody a complex of professional qualities, knowledge, skills and qualifications, and values that are inherent in specialists in both fields.

Conclusion. One of the important conditions for successfully solving the current issues set for the comprehensive development and improvement of the country is the development of the spiritual, educational and cultural level of the people. Because the higher the spiritual, educational and cultural level of each member of the people and society, the higher the human potential, the higher the standard of living of the people. Therefore, paying special attention to raising the cultural, spiritual and moral level of our people and society is one of our important tasks.

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